

Mobile Assistance Language Learning: A Case Study of Teaching Using Edmodo

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Abstract:- This research aims to optimize the teaching and learning of using Edmodo. Edmodo is an easy and safe model for students to connect and collaborate, share content videos; images; and access to work on college assignments, provide assessments and notice. The design of this study is action research. The subjects in this study are lecturer and regular students who are involved in Teaching English for Young Learners. The research phase will be used in this study is an adaptation of the Kemmis and Taggart (1988) model which includes; planning, action, observation and reflection. The research has been carried out in two cycles, each cycle consists of three meetings. Research instruments are using observation, document analysis, interview, quiz and questionnaire. The results of the research shows classroom action research which aims to optimize the use of Edmodo in language learning successfully implemented. Lecturers can use and do process improvements, and enhance activity and creativity in language learning. From the students' side, they can attend lectures with Edmodo. Activities and creativity in learning this subject become more interested. Students are very motivated in following the recovery by using Edmodo. They are motivated to complete the task precisely on due time.

Keywords:- mobile assistance language learning, edmodo.

I. INTRODUCTION

In today's globalized world, English is as a lingua franca. English is learned as a foreign language for in Indonesia, which until now the learning process is still ongoing (Sari D. M., 2019). In teaching foreign languages, teachers are required to be communicative to their students. The goal is the students will be more active in using English as a foreign language. It also faced by the students of university who learn English as a second language (Sari D. M., 2019). Teaching can guide and facilitate the students to study and learn, enable the students to learn, and set conditions for learning. In teaching, the teacher informs the students what they learned before increasing the knowledge that they have gained (Sari D. M., 2019). Countries worldwide have made English as one of the compulsory subjects in schools. The teachers progress ensuring the best pedagogies and teaching methods that involve more social context in English learning as a foreign language (Woo & Reeves, 2007). Realizing the condition above, the practitioner in foreign language education should find any possible solution in delivering the best teaching methods and strategies in teaching English as a second language (Sari D. M., 2016). Information technology can not be denied has made a large contribution in improving the

quality of education both in academics, administration and management. The use of the web internet in the world of education is widely used in higher education is e-learning. Classroom learning is considered demanding on integrating the technology (Erben, Ban, & Castaneda, 2009).

Along with the rapid development of technology, it is now common to find students coming to class with the latest technological tools such as smartphones, laptops, or other handheld devices to gain knowledge or to communicate with one another (Zayed, 2015). It changes the way in the educational approach from the conventional way to a more comprehensive, communicative and technological way (Mochtar F. A., 2016). With the advancement of technology and the web that is fast and effective in many fields, many teachers use technology in their teaching to develop students' language skills (Al Naibi, AL Jabri, & Al Kalbali, 2018). Hadiyanto (2013) states that the use of the pursuit with e-learning has provided time space, study space and facilities from physical form to virtual form. In addition to language skills, the use of technology in the classroom can improve students' 21st century skills. Technology also forms the basis among the most important factors influencing lifelong learning (Ersoz, Kucuksuleymanoolu, & Ersoz, 2017).

One that can be integrated with the help of technology in learning is the use of digital teaching materials or electronic teaching materials, either in the form of books, modules, student worksheets, and so on (Al Kathiri, 2015). Teaching materials are one of the important components in language learning (Sari & Prasetyo, 2021). Completing the teaching materials will help strengthen the content and interest of students by providing various explanations and exercises and expand the material by adding other elements that are useful for students. Digital or electronic teaching materials can be integrated with social networking sites by affixing links for students to use. The development of social networking sites has created communication tools to help many methods that can be applied in teaching and learning (Beltran-cruz & Cruz, 2013). The use of social networking sites in this learning can be called Social Learning Networks or abbreviated SLN. Examples of these sites include Edmodo, Ning, Elgg, Kahoot, ClassDojo, Classcraft, Socrative and ValuePulse. SLN has advantages over SNS (such as facebook, twitter, etc.) namely minimizing security and privacy issues that can arise when using SNS and allowing teachers and students to use social networking technology for educational purposes (Brady, Holcomb, & SMith, 2010).

By adapting the habits of students who always access cellular phones or smartphones, it is better if learning English is done using the MALL (Mobile Assisted Language Learning) approach, which is an approach using mobile devices for teaching and learning activities (Lindaman & Nolan, 2015), so that not only can accommodate learning in the neo-millennial generation but can also provide learning anytime and anywhere in accordance with the original nature of the neo-millennial generation. With the aim of making improvements to the English learning system in schools using the MALL approach and introducing media to MALL that can be applied in schools as a medium for learning and developing skills students in learning English. On the basis of the popularity, effectiveness, efficiency, and benefits of cell phones, many experts say and agree that the Mobile Assisted Language Learning (MALL) approach, which is an approach using mobile devices for teaching and learning activities is very effective to use. in developing and teaching English learning to the neo-millennial generation. Learning using this approach can also create a real learning environment for students and is very in line with the nature of the neo-millennial generation who are very familiar with the use of technology and social media so that learning can be done anywhere and anytime (Boholano, 2017).

Of the various kinds of SLN that teachers can use in the learning process, Edmodo is one of the popular learning management systems (Durak, Cankaya, Yunkul, & Ozturk, 2017). Edmodo is basically a web application similar to Facebook but provides educational tools instead of a social media platform (Flanigan, 2012). This app was founded and maintained by Jeff O'Hara and Nic Borg with the aim of creating an online learning environment for teachers and students. It was first tested in 2008 and is available for use afterwards. This application was also recognized by the American Association of School Librarians in 2011 as one of the top 25 websites that foster quality innovation, active participation, creativity and collaboration in the category entitled 'Social Networking and Communication'. The facilitator that can be played by the teacher in learning using Edmodo-assisted teaching materials is by posting learning materials, learning notes, giving assignments, evaluating students and communicating through Edmodo if learning is not taking place in class (Trust, 2012). Learning using these teaching materials is also effective for increasing motivation in lifelong learning, increasing teacher-student interaction, and helping people fulfill self-realization. Edmodo application is an application that can help the student-centered learning process. students can follow their improvement through the assessment report and they can see the results and get feedback from their teacher through the application (Yagci, 2015).

E-learning is a process effective learning produced by combining the delivery of material digital consisting of support and services in learning (Barbara, P, & all, 2008). Using Edmodo, the teacher and the students can reach out to one another and connect by sharing ideas, problems, and helpful tips (Shams-Abadi, Ahmadi, & Mehrdad, 2015). By applying e-learning Edmodo, both teacher and students can reach out to one another and connect out by sharing some

ideas, solve some problems, and helpful various tips. A teacher can assign and grade the work on e-learning Edmodo; the students can get the valuable helpful from the entire class on e-learning Edmodo (Mills & Chandra, 2011). Edmodo is one of the E-learning based learning models which is provided free of charge. Edmodo is almost similar to Facebook. It designed very modestly and easy. It also provides a space for teachers, students, and even parents to optimize the teaching and learning process (Kongchan, 2013). Edmodo might be one of the best platforms for social network and academic pursuits. It is a website for educational usage that adapts the idea of a social network and transforms it into a site suitable for the classroom, regardless of students' ages or the institutional level (Mochtar & Dzakiria, 2015).

Based on the benefits obtained by online communication media and important features possessed by edmodo, the researcher is interested in examining and also investigating students' perceptions of using edmodo as a communication tool in learning. From the description of the background, the first stage of this research can be some problems are formulated as follows:

- How is the way to develop mobile assistance language learning using Edmodo?
- How is the motivation and attitude of students in using Edmodo?
- What is the student response to mobile assistance language learning of Edmodo?

II. RESEARCH METHOD

The design of this study is action research. Therefore this research is maximizing and finding solutions to problems that arise in the use of Edmodo in teaching Research and ELT subjects, then research This class action is included in the scope of applied research. The main approach in classroom action research is a qualitative method (Creswell, 2003). Qualitative data will find and report on teaching and learning strategies, processes improvement and actions taken in finding solutions to mobile assistance language learning expectations. Whereas quantitative data is as additional data to study motivation and attitude of students after the implementation of mobile assistance of language learning.

The research phase that will be used in this research is the Kemmis model and Taggart (1988) divide the action research procedure into four activity stages in one cycle (cycle), namely: 1. Planning, 2. Actions, 3. Observe, and 4. Reflection.

Fig. 1: Classroom Action Research Cycles

The research will be carried out on the STKIP PGRI Sidoarjo English Language Education program. One of the main principles of classroom action research is lecturer who takes course is directly involved in the teaching model applied. The subjects in this study were lecturer (the researcher herself) and regular students who are involved in teaching and learning with the Teaching English for Young Learners using Edmodo media as a basis for E-learning models. The subject of this research was taken in one class, which consisted of 30 students with a purposive sampling data (Creswell, 2003).

There are four types of instruments that will be used in this study:

- Observation (Creswell, 2003). The data taken from observations by researcher from the teaching and learning process through Edmodo.
- Document Analysis (Creswell, 2003). The data were taken from the documents posted from the lecturer's and students' posts in e-learning Edmodo.
- Interview (Heigham & Croker, 2009). The focus group interviews with a semi-structured design were utilized to get the data for students' engagement
- Quiz Data. Quizzes will be taken at the end of each cycle
- Questionnaire (Heigham & Croker, 2009). The open-ended questionnaire were used to check students' opinion about teaching-learning process by using Edmodo.

First, the data were collected through the observations. Second, the data were collected from the documents posted both by the lecturer and students' posts in Edmodo. Next, the data administered from the focus group interviews and given quizzes at the end of each cycle, then finally the researcher distributed the questionnaires to the students.

The data analysis was conducted by adapting Creswell's theory (2003) as well. It began with some steps, such as preparing and organizing the data, then the steps will followed by reading those data to get the general senses. Moreover, the researchers was coding the data, then generating the description of the whole data, and finally the researchers representing the description of the whole data. Another step was interpreting the data and finally presenting the whole of the data. After collecting the data from the five instruments, then it validated by triangulation (Silverman, 2005). Triangulation was regarded significant and crucial as an effort to make sure that the data collected from the observations, focus group interviews, documents, quizzes and questionnaires were matched each other.

III. DISCUSSION

The Implementation of Edmodo in TEYL class.

A. Cycle 1: Planning and Action

In 1st week teaching using Edmodo, the lecturer presents Edmodo account creation. Then the lecturer explains about edmodo and learning features which will be used by lecturer and students to carry out learning activities. Then the lecturer asked students to create Edmodo accounts. On 2nd week, the lecturer displays the steps in using Edmodo in learning. The learning steps are carried out as follows, the lecturer tries using several functions, the student teaches or performs instructions by using several functions in Edmodo. In 3rd week, the lecturer gave an explanation of the definition of young learners in class, then the lecturer gives assignments through edmodo about the definition of young learners

Fig. 2: Edmodo Social Networks

a) Observation

During the partial observation process, among students had a problem with registers successfully addressed at the third meeting. Another facility provided by Edmodo was meaningful and interaction tasks. Note menu provided the opportunities for the teacher and the students to interact by posting something or giving comments to a post. The interaction can also took place when the students post or ask genuine questions to the lecture such as when they find difficulties to access e-learning Edmodo features. The interaction in communication among technology is a basic requirement in language-based teaching and learning (Bates, 2005). From the observation in the classroom, it begin with observe student activities in submitting assignments with deadlines that have been determined. After observation, it turns out that many students are wrong of turn in assignments and some have not posted or collected any task at all. But most of the enthusiasm was apparent from a number of comments during their turn in assignment.

b) Reflection

Based on the learning actions taken, we can see several of the cycle one, some of the steps of teaching using edmodo are done well such as poses register, making Teaching English for Young Learners (TEYL) class courses, create libraries and add books, assign assignments to students and explain the functions of the features that will be used in learning with Edmodo. However, there are some weaknesses in cycle 1 that need to anticipate in the second teaching cycle. These weaknesses are as follows: first, the students forget the password to enter Edmodo at the 2nd meeting; second, some students don't know how to collect online assignments to Edmodo; third, the students get the wrong way to collect assignments, they post on the wall.

B. Cycle 2: Planning and Action

In 1st week of teaching in cycle 2 using Edmodo, the lecturer returns presentation of the Edmodo account within the class to explain and solve problems that arise in the first cycle. Those are, reset the password for students who forget password and demonstrate how to collect assignments correctly. Then the lecturer presents search and use learning resources from Edmodo and linking to them. This is also the lecturer finally correcting and guiding students to write characteristics of young learners. So the lecturer asked students to submit characteristics of young learners. In 2nd week, learning activities using Edmodo took place better and smoother. Students successfully turn in assignments correctly and on time. On 3rd week, the lecturer gives an explanation of the class management of young learners as a whole in the classroom, so the lecturer gives assignment through edmodo about class management of young learners

Fig. 3: Features of Edmodo

a) Observation

After lecturing in class about classroom management of young learners, it begin to be continued by observing students' activities in submitting assignments with predetermined deadlines. Furthermore, e-learning Edmodo through menu of note also facilitated the cognitive processes for the students in the teaching and learning process. The cognitive processes such as synthesizing ideas, composing, and publishing writing are the forms of various activities of order thinking (Krathwohl, 2002). The students can collect (turn in) tasks on

time. But mostly looked enthusiastic seen from some of their comments when making a turn in the assignment.

b) Reflection

In this second cycle, almost all of the students encountered no problems in use Edmodo to maximize the teaching of Teaching English for Young Learners (TEYL). However, there are some features that haven't been used up to this second cycle.

• The students' motivation and attitude of using Edmodo in class

The lecturer gives questions related to their motivation using Edmodo in teaching subject of Teaching English for Young Learners (TEYL). The question is 'Is Edmodo giving you motivation in teaching and learning activities? If yes, How does Edmodo motivate you in this course?'. Of the 28 lecturing participants registered with Edmodo, 21 among them are giving answers that basically Edmodo can give encouraging them to learn, complete their assignments, read resources which is posted by the lecturer and gives the desire and courage to ask questions. Edmodo as an easy and simplicity application in learning are also admitted by the students. These two strengths have actually been admitted by some previous of the studies conducted earlier (Adas & Bakir, 2013)

To provide a clearer picture of student learning outcomes, then the data is presented as follows:

Diagram 1: Students' Performance For Courses

For diagram above, it can be interpreted as follows, the level of student attendance in classes are indeed average performance indicators because they can reach an average of 13 times. Means student attendance in class in one semester increased 81.65%. For the average value of assignments achieved by students amounted to 83.37%. Average of mid-semester scores are 81.94%, meaning that there is good progress for students in taking mid-semester. This student can be caused by a better motivation and happy atmosphere. For the average of final semester are 80.78%, meaning that the output learning was good.

There are also those who say that with Edmodo, they are more diligent in learning from the sources provided, so that they can reduce their laziness in doing task. Because they realized that the lecturer could see anyone those who

have done the assignments and those who have not. Coupled with seeing deadline the tasks listed on Edmodo are able to spur them to complete the assignment precisely time. The students were also in agreement that Edmodo gave them unlimited space and time for learning such as learning from gadgets, smartphones, laptops and learning in leisure time. Rosenberg (2001) acknowledges this as learning method technology which has made learning accessible almost anywhere and anytime and available 24 hours a day.

• **The students’ response of using Edmodo in class**

The students were also asked to fill out a questionnaire containing an assessment on the online lecture material they have just obtained. The results of the questionnaire are presented in the following diagram:

Diagram 2: Students’ response of teaching material

Based on the data above, student responses to the use of teaching materials using several assessment indicators in the communication aspect visual for content attractiveness 80.7% of students answered good and very well, for form communication 82.9% of students answered good and very well, for ease of use 85.2% of students answered good and very well, for indicators of writing clarity 82.8% students answered good and very well, for indicators of audio clarity 83% of students answered good and very well and the last indicator was the ease of understanding 86.4% of students good and very good answer. The average answer of students who answered good and very good against the six indicators is 83.5%. If you look at the performance indicators up front. As has been determined, the student's response is said to be positive if 75% of the students answered good for the use of video tutorial-based teaching materials. In aspect assessment of visual communication, the average student answers for the good and very good categories are 83.5% far above 75% means the student's assessment or response to the process learning materials is positive. It means the use of teaching materials in student learning activities make a positive contribution or a happy atmosphere for students in participating in activities study or lecture. So it can be concluded that the use of teaching materials in terms of aspects visual communication is considered good and positive by students taking courses.

Diagram 3: Students’ responses of learning design

Student responses from the learning design for indicators of the relevance of learning objectives, the number of students who answered good and very good 87.5%. Then for the indicator of the relevance of learning benefits, the number of students who answered good and very well 83%. For material relevance indicators learning, students who answered good and very well 90.8%. For relevance indicators characteristics of students, who answered good and very well 86.3%. And the last indicator, students who answered good and very well 77.2%. Of the five design indicators learning, the average student who answered well and very well was 84.96%. because of numbers an average of 84.96% is greater than the average number of performance indicators (75%), then the response students towards teaching materials from the aspect of learning design are positive, meaning that the learning design aspects according to students' views have a contribution and are able to make students feel happy in participating learning activities.

The following are some responses from students regarding attitudes from lecturing participants posted via Edmodo: The students' response in using Edmodo for Teaching English for Young Learners (TEYL) as a whole was good. Most of them say using Edmodo provides its own advantages in learning activities and doing their job. Some responses from them reveal that, if they are absent from class, they can still attend the teaching material given by lecturer through Edmodo, so that they do not miss both in terms of material learning and in working on assignments given by the lecturer. Some of them respond in the same way, they can choose the right time and place for follow the continuation of lectures and assignments submitted through Edmodo. Some of them also stated that using Edmodo is easy and interesting, even there some students said that lectures through Edmodo were more effective than either in terms of time and cost. Student responses to questions related to the attitude 'Is Edmodo interesting and Enjoyable?'. The results of this study generally revealed that lectures could run E-learning with Edmodo. The lecturer succeeded in guiding the students inside use of Edmodo main functions or features, such as creating an account at Edmodo, login and log, post notes, tasks, quizzes, polls, interact with students and putting teaching materials in Edmodo Library. After lecturer and students understand and be able to use all the features, the lecturer could optimize the teaching and learning process of Teaching English for Young Learners courses. From the

student's side, it was also seen they could attend e-learning lectures with Edmodo, this can be seen from the number of study participants joined in the group, submit assignments, and carry out quizzes with Edmodo. Students can also participate in polls conducted by lecturers. From the perception of students about the technical aspects of Edmodo it was revealed that a large number of positive statements about the use of Edmodo in lectures. Meanwhile the students' perceptions about Edmodo features stated that they could and liked to use it even though these features are not used in lectures.

The use of Edmodo in the Teaching English for Young Learners (TEYL) subject is capable maximizing students' learning activities. Precisely Edmodo is more effectively than face to face teaching-learning model. This learning with using Edmodo, students are encouraged to independent learning, inquiry learning, active learning and explorative learning. Lecturers easily control students' progress assignments via Edmodo. Teaching materials using mobile devices and the Edmodo application can be used according to the time set in learning. This is because in the application there is a time setting for students to upload their assignments.

In addition to filling out the questionnaire, the results of the study were also obtained from the results of interviews with teachers who used language teaching materials with mobile devices and the Edmodo application. The results of the interview are as follows. First, learning using teaching materials using mobile devices and the Edmodo application is very good to be applied at this time. Because today's students are a picture of "Digital Natives", "Millennials", and "The Net Generation". Smartphones and tablets have also been found. In the learning process, more than 90% of students already use smartphones or tablets that are brought to school. Based on research by previous experts, in Japan currently has set a goal for a 100% usage rate by 2020 for the use of smartphones and other mobile devices in the learning process from Elementary School to University. Second, students are more motivated in learning activities. This is because the teaching materials are equipped with various kinds of images, audio, and video. In addition, Edmodo can help students work on assignments anytime and anywhere. Edmodo is very useful because they can access classroom resources and can communicate with teachers privately whenever they want outside of the classroom (Fujimoto, 2012).

Third, the Edmodo application is easy to use because the display is almost similar to the appearance of Facebook. According to explanations, several sources say that Edmodo is a social networking site with a layout and design that is very similar to Facebook. However, edmodo is much more private and secure for learning environment as it allows only teachers to create and manage accounts, and only their students, who receive the group code and register in the group, can access and join the group. Fourth, although it has many advantages, the use of teaching materials with mobile devices and the Edmodo application also has limitations in being able to apply in class. The limitation is that the teaching materials must be developed

by the teacher themselves, but the preparation of teaching and evaluation materials that are integrated into Edmodo takes time. It was found that teachers have difficulty developing their own teaching materials, this is because teachers do not yet have the ability to develop their own teaching materials. Fifth, the interactions that occur in the Edmodo application between teachers and students have a negative effect if students cannot use polite and courteous language in conveying questions, responses, and so on. This can happen, because in the application, teachers and students are in a position of friendship. This situation can lead to role conflict and weaken the teacher's authority (Warner & Esposito, 2009).

Sixth, the learning process requires an internet connection. If the student does not have internet package, then the learning process can be stopped. This becomes an obstacle if the school is also not provided with an internet network that can be used by students. Internet has become an increasingly important feature of the learning environment for students. The use of the Edmodo application or other educational platforms for students to register and complete their daily or weekly assignments can only be done via the internet (Khodary, 2017). Students can improve themselves from any location with access to the Internet by receiving any education they want. Seventh, mobile devices or smart phones used by students can distract students (eg, sending messages, playing games, surfing social media, etc.). So that teachers must be able to control the learning process through Edmodo and provide sufficient allocations for students in completing their assignments. Because the learning process uses Edmodo, the teacher determines the content and the learning process must be carried out for the specified time duration.

IV. CONCLUSION

Based on the results of research and discussion, it can be concluded that teaching materials using mobile devices and the Edmodo application are one of the variations of teaching materials that can be used in learning Indonesian. The teaching materials are very easy to use, so that it can make it easier for teachers to achieve learning objectives and deliver learning materials. Learning using these teaching materials is student-centered, so the teacher functions as a facilitator in the learning process. The teaching materials can be used according to the time set based on the lesson plan. Apart from some of the advantages described, there are limitations to these teaching materials, such as limited internet connections, students' attention can be distracted, interactions that are built need courtesy between students and teachers, and other limitations. The use of Indonesian language teaching materials using mobile devices and the Edmodo application is highly recommended for use in this century, because students are more motivated in learning and improving student skills. Recommendations for further research is to try the application of other social networking applications to see the advantages and disadvantages in language learning, applications such as Kahoot and Moodle are highly recommended. Regarding the findings of this research, a number of considerations are suggested. First,

lecturers can use Edmodo as an alternative media in e-learning model. Second, Classroom Action Research must be carried out continuously to improve the effectiveness in increasing students' participation in learning, learning composition group on Edmodo and in a real class. Third, the next researcher can also examine the effectiveness of using Edmodo in lectures, whether experimental research, surveys or other research designs, with the aim to see and develop knowledge related to e-learning from all sides.

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